

EOSC-IF

Accounting for Services interoperability Guideline

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EOSC-IF / EOSC Accounting for Services interoperability Guideline

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Abstract

The Accounting Service is a robust platform designed to streamline metric collection, aggregation, and exchange across diverse infrastructures, providers, and projects. Our comprehensive solution offers a REST API, empowering clients to seamlessly integrate their metrics into the system. This API accepts input from various resources, securely stores it in a database, and performs intelligent aggregation of incoming data.

Clients can harness the power of our REST API to integrate their data seamlessly, ensuring a cohesive experience across different environments. This integration capability facilitates efficient collaboration and data sharing among various entities. The API resources are exclusively accessible to authenticated clients, ensuring the security of sensitive metric data.

Moreover, our platform provides an intuitive user interface, enabling clients to interact effortlessly with the Accounting Service. Users can access and manage accounting data for specific time periods through a user-friendly dashboard.

Version History

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Glossary

EOSC Future project Glossary is incorporated by reference: <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/x/JQCK>

1. Intended Audience

Technical experts of service and resource providers who would like their services and/or resources to be interoperable or integrate with EOSC-Core Services. The main target audience for this document are service owners who wish to publish accounting data to EOSC.

2. Description and main features

The EOSC Accounting Service is a platform designed to efficiently collect, aggregate, and exchange metrics across various infrastructures, providers, and projects. The system provides a REST API, which accepts input from diverse resources, stores it in a database, and aggregates the incoming data. It also offers an intuitive user interface that allows clients to interact with the platform and access accounting data for specific time periods. All API resources are only accessible to authenticated clients, ensuring secure access to sensitive data.

The key functionalities offered by the EOSC Accounting Service are:

- Efficient collection, aggregation, and exchange of metrics.
- REST API that accepts input from diverse resources.
- Database storage and aggregation of incoming data.
- Intuitive user interface for accessing accounting data.
- Secure access to sensitive data through authenticated clients.

Fundamentals - Elements of the Service

The Accounting Service is a system that provides a framework for organising and managing accounting data for a specific project, provider or installation. It involves various roles such as Project Admin, Provider Admin, and Installation Admin, each with their specific set of responsibilities.

One of the key elements of the Accounting Service is Metrics, which are quantitative measures used to assess and track the performance or usage of a service. A Metric Definition is a way of representing and describing the type of metric.

In the Accounting Service, Metric and Unit Type are essential components that allow for the collection and tracking of various types of Metrics. These types are included as part of the Metric Definition and provide greater flexibility and specificity in the Metrics that the Accounting System can collect. A Metric Type defines how physical quantities are collected over time, while a Unit Type expresses and measures physical quantities used in various infrastructures, service providers, and projects. Together, these elements enable users to gather and analyse data at different levels of granularity and with different units of measurement.

The Accounting System allows the client to create a hierarchical structure consisting of three levels: **Project, Provider, and Installation**. The Project is the main resource of the system, and clients can create it by registering their unique European Project ID. Providers are organisations that offer at least one installation to a specific project, and they can be registered through the EOSC Resource Catalogue and created directly through the Accounting Service. Installations are specific instances or parts of a resource/service that are allocated to a specific project by a Provider. An Installation can be associated with a Resource, which can be retrieved from the EOSC Resource Catalogue. The Accounting System communicates with the Resource Catalogue to retrieve the available Resources and stores specific information about a Resource.

This hierarchical structure allows clients to organise and manage accounting data for their project and enables them to easily view and analyse metrics at different levels of granularity.

Access to the Service (Authentication & Authorization)

The authentication process for the Accounting Service is performed via the EOSC AAI Core Infrastructure Proxy. The EOSC AAI Core Infrastructure Proxy is a centralised authentication system that provides a single sign-on (SSO) mechanism for accessing the EOSC Core services and resources. When a user attempts to access the Accounting Service, they are redirected to the EOSC AAI Core Infrastructure Proxy, where they must authenticate themselves using their credentials (such as username and password). Once authenticated, it generates a security token that is used to verify the user's identity and authorization when accessing the Accounting System. The use of the EOSC AAI Core Infrastructure Proxy provides several benefits for the Accounting Service, including increased security, simplified authentication, and integration with other EOSC services and resources.

On the other hand, the authorization process is handled through the Accounting Service. When clients access the Accounting Service, they must provide valid authentication credentials to access the system. The Accounting Service verifies the credentials, and if they are valid, grants the client access to the resources they are authorised to access.

The authorization system also includes role-based access control (RBAC), which allows clients to specify different levels of access for different clients.

RBAC is a widely used approach to access control that grants access based on the roles and responsibilities of individual users within an organisation. In the context of the Accounting Service, RBAC allows clients to define specific roles for different types of users, such as project admin, provider admin, and installation admin. Each role is associated with a set of permissions that determine what actions the client can perform and what data they can access. By using RBAC, the Accounting Service provides a granular level of access control that helps ensure the security and privacy of sensitive accounting data.

Project Admin Role

The main role of the Accounting Service is the project admin, who is responsible for managing accounting data for their assigned projects. As the project admin, the client has access to a wide range of features and functions within the Accounting Service, including the ability to create, view and edit accounting data and manage user access and permissions. Once a client has been granted the project admin role for a specific project, the client is able to generate their own preferred hierarchical structure (Figure 1) within the Accounting System and insert new metrics on this structure.

Figure 1. Hierarchical structure

The hierarchical structure within the Accounting Service allows the project admin to define the relationships between different components within their project, such as providers, installations, and metrics. Additionally, they are able to associate Resources with Installations. This structure provides a framework for organising and managing accounting data for the project, and allows users to easily view and analyse metrics at different levels of granularity.

Provider Admin Role

The provider admin role is responsible for managing the providers that belong in the hierarchical structure created by the project admin, as well as the associated accounting data for those providers.

The provider admin may have permissions to modify providers within the hierarchical structure, as well as manage the associated accounting data. This role is important for ensuring that the providers are accurately represented within the Accounting Service and that their accounting data is properly managed and accounted for.

The provider admin may also have permissions to add, modify, or remove installations within the hierarchical structure, as well as manage the associated accounting data.

Installation Admin Role

The installation admin role is responsible for managing one or more installations that belong to the hierarchical structure created by the project admin or provider admin. They may have permissions to modify installations within the hierarchical structure, as well as manage the associated accounting data for those installations.

Actions available

Once the client creates their preferable hierarchical structure, they can insert metrics from various resources, including projects, installations, and providers. This functionality expands the Accounting

Service versatility and allows for a more comprehensive collection and analysis of metrics from a broader range of sources.

By providing this capability, the Accounting Service can enable clients to monitor and optimise their resources' performance more effectively. With a broader range of metrics available, clients can gain deeper insights into their infrastructure, identify bottlenecks or other issues, and make data-driven decisions to optimise their operations.

Additionally, the Accounting Service collects different types of metrics. This feature is highly valuable as it enables the platform to collect and analyse a wide range of metrics to provide clients with comprehensive insights into their resources' performance. By collecting different types of metrics, the platform can provide a more holistic view of resource performance and enable clients to make informed decisions about resource allocation, cost optimization, and sustainability.

A **metric** in Accounting for Services has the following structure:

- ***metric_definition_id***

This field is likely a unique identifier associated with the type or definition of the metric. It could reference a predefined set of metrics, helping to categorise and identify the nature of the data being reported.

- ***time_period_start*** and ***time_period_end***

These fields define the start and end timestamps of the time period during which the metric was measured. The timestamps are in Zulu format ("2022-01-05T09:13:07Z"), indicating a standardised and internationally recognized datetime representation.

- ***value***

This field represents the actual numerical value of the metric. In the example, it's set to "10.2," suggesting a quantitative measure associated with the defined metric for the given time period.

```
{
  "metric_definition_id": "507f1f77bcf86cd799439011",
  "time_period_start": "2022-01-05T09:13:07Z",
  "time_period_end": "2022-01-05T09:13:07Z",
  "value": 10.2
}
```

A Metric Definition has the following structure:

```
{
  "metric_name": "# of PID prefixes to be deleted",
  "metric_description": "number of PID prefixes",
  "unit_type": "#",
  "metric_type": "count"
}
```

Integrations with other EOSC Services

The EOSC Accounting Service is designed to integrate with a variety of other EOSC components and services. The service integrates with an EOSC AAI Core Infrastructure Proxy to authenticate clients and manage access to sensitive data. By using an EOSC AAI Core Infrastructure Proxy to authenticate clients, the EOSC Accounting Service can ensure that only authorised users are able to access sensitive accounting data. This helps to prevent unauthorised access and data breaches, and ensures that usage metrics are collected and reported accurately and securely.

It also integrates with the EOSC Service Registry to retrieve information about Providers and Services such as their name, description, unique identifier. This information can be used to enrich the accounting data collected by the Accounting Service, providing additional context and metadata about the resources being used.

3. Response to Community Need

Two needs have been identified:

1. Services operated by Providers that do not have easy access to accounting solutions, and would benefit from integrating with a federated accounting service.
2. Providing Service metadata in a Resource Catalogue alone may not be sufficient to convince a user that the service is valuable. Publishing an accounting dashboard for a service can increase the confidence of a potential user of a service, that the service/resource is actively supported and widely used.

4. High-level Service Architecture

The Accounting Service is responsible for collecting data from a variety of sources, including different resources, projects, providers, and installations. This data is collected and processed in a centralised database, allowing clients to access and analyse accounting data across multiple systems and projects.

Figure 2. High-Level Architecture

The Accounting Service architecture is structured as follows:

Functional aspects

1. **User Interface:** The user interface is the primary point of interaction for clients to access the Accounting Service. It provides a graphical interface that allows users to view and interact with accounting data.
2. **REST API:** The REST API is the main entry point for incoming accounting data from diverse resources. It receives input data from external systems and stores it in the database. The API is responsible for aggregating and processing the data, making it available for querying through the user interface.
3. **Authentication and Authorization:** The Accounting Service uses the EOSC AAI Proxy for authentication, which provides a single sign-on mechanism for clients to access the service. Once authenticated, clients are granted access to the system based on their role-based access control (RBAC) permissions. The authorization system is responsible for managing user access and permissions and enforcing security policies.
4. **Database:** The database is the primary storage for accounting data. It receives incoming data from the REST API and stores it in a structured format that enables efficient querying and reporting. The database also supports data aggregation, which allows for the calculation of metrics.

Non functional aspects

1. **Integration and Interoperability:** The Accounting Service is designed to integrate with other systems and services within the EOSC ecosystem. It provides APIs for external systems to access accounting data, and it can also consume data from other systems to enrich its own data. The Accounting Service also supports interoperability with different infrastructure providers and projects, enabling seamless data exchange and aggregation.
2. **High Availability:** high availability for the Accounting API involves ensuring that the API is always available to handle requests, even in the face of hardware failures, network outages, and other types of disruptions. Our high-availability architecture contains :
 - a. **Load Balancing:** Deploying multiple instances of the API and using a load balancer to distribute requests across them, ensuring that no single instance is overloaded.
 - b. **Replication:** Maintaining copies of the API's data and code across multiple servers, so that if one server fails, another can take over seamlessly.
 - c. **Monitoring and Alerting:** Continuously monitoring the API and sending alerts if any issues arise.

5. Definitions

<i>Term</i>	<i>Definition</i>
Client	As a client we define either a user or a service that communicates and interacts with the Accounting Service
Metric Definition	Metric Definition is the way to represent and describe the type of the metrics
Project	A Project is the main resource of the Accounting Service. The first step a user must follow is to create a project under which the metric data will belong
Provider	As Provider, we refer to the Organisation that offers at least one installation to a specific project
Installation	We use the term installation as it is defined in the Virtual Access documentation to refer to a specific instance or part of a resource/service that is allocated to a specific Project by one Provider
Resource	Each Installation may be associated with a Resource available in EOSC Resource Catalogue.
Metric	A metric is a quantifiable measure used to track and evaluate the performance, progress, or quality of a specific process, project, or system
Metric Type	A Metric Type determines how the physical quantities are collected over longer time windows
Unit Type	A Unit Type expresses and measures physical quantities used in various infrastructures, service providers, and projects

6. Licensing Information

This may be required if the subject of the Interoperability Guideline comprises software components.

Component	Product/Software Used	Licence
API	Quarkus	Apache 2.0
Load Balancer	Haproxy	GPL/LGPL
UI	Symfony PHP	MIT licence.
Data Store	MongoDB	Server Side Public License

7. Adopted Standards

Table 9-1: Adopted Standards

Resource Type	Short Description	References
REST	All the endpoints exposed by the Accounting Service follow the REST standard.	https://www.ics.uci.edu/~fielding/pubs/
HTTPS	User interface of the Accounting Service is exposed via the HTTPs Protocol.	https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc2818
OpenAPI	All endpoints of the Accounting Service are described through the OpenAPI specification.	https://www.openapis.org/what-is-openapi
OpenID Connect Protocol	It allows both Accounting Service and User Interface to verify the identity of the clients based on the authentication performed by AAI Proxy.	https://openid.net/connect
Quarkus	It is a Java framework optimised for a fast startup time and low memory usage. It is a great choice for building REST APIs thanks to its lightweight and efficient design. The Accounting Service API has been built using Quarkus.	https://quarkus.io
HAProxy	It is a load balancer responsible for distributing incoming traffic to multiple servers and ensuring the availability and scalability of Accounting Service.	https://www.haproxy.org
Apache Server	Apache server is used as a reverse proxy that sits between the client and the Accounting Service, forwarding client requests to the Accounting Service and returning the server's response to the client.	https://httpd.apache.org

8. Integration Options

EOSC Accounting for service offers 3 integration options: Integration Option 1: Integrate with an aggregator of accounting data, Integration Option 2: Integrate with a Single Provider and Integration Option 3: Make use of Accounting data: Which are described below.

8.1. Integration Option 1: Integrate with an aggregator of accounting data

Integration Steps:

1. **Project Registration:** The Accounting Service Admin registers the "Openaire" project. Along with the unique European Project ID, it is stored in the Accounting Service. Upon successful project registration, [it is assigned to a particular Project Admin](#).
2. **Provider Registration:** The Project Admin identifies and [registers](#) several providers participating in the project. Each provider is associated with the project, linking them to the Openaire.
3. **Installation Setup:** Project Admin, for each provider [configure installations](#) within the Accounting Service. Each installation is associated with a provider and linked to the Openaire and it may be associated with a specific Resource from EOSC resource catalogue. [Provider Admin](#) can also configure installations but only to their providers.
4. **Metric Definitions:** Metric Definitions [are created](#) to define the specific metrics that need to be tracked for the project.
5. **Metric Types and Unit Types:** [Metric Types](#) are defined to categorise and standardise the metrics. [Unit Types](#) specify the units of measurement.
6. **Data Collection and Integration:** The Installations or Resources collect the data that is important to be measured and analysed by the Accounting Service. This data is then integrated into the Accounting Service using [API's endpoints](#) or [User Interface](#).
7. **Data Analysis:** Project Admins (Provider and Installation Admins can also access the data based on the granted permissions) can now access the Accounting Service to view and analyse metrics at different levels: High-level project metrics. Provider-specific metrics to assess the performance of each service provider. Installation-level metrics to gain insights into the performance of individual installations.
8. **User Management:** The Project Admin has the authority to [manage](#) users and permissions at all levels of the Accounting Service (Project, Provider, and Installation). They can invite and grant access to other users, including Provider Admins, Installation Admins, and additional Project Admins.

8.2. Integration Option 2: Integrate with a Single Provider

In this context, the Project Admin has already registered the Providers to the project, and a Provider Admin is granted permission to access and manage data at the Provider level within the Accounting Service.

Integration Steps:

1. **Provider Admin Access:** The [Provider Admin](#) is granted access to the Accounting Service at the Provider level by the Project Admin of the Openaire project.
2. **Review Provider Information:** The Provider Admin reviews and confirms the details of the [provider](#) within the Accounting Service, ensuring accuracy in provider information and project associations.
3. **Installation Setup:** The Provider Admin can access the installations associated with the provider within the Accounting Service. They can also set up [installations](#) and manage them.
4. **Data Collection and Integration:** The Provider Admin oversees the integration of data from the [installations](#) belonging to the [Provider](#). All relevant metrics are integrated into the Accounting Service using APIs or User Interface.
5. **Data Analysis and Reporting:** Provider Admins can access the Accounting Service to view and analyse metrics at the Provider level. They can track the performance of their installations associated with their provider entity.

6. User Management: The Provider Admin has the authority to [manage](#) users within their provider entity. They can invite and grant access to other users, such as team members or additional Provider Admins and Installation Admins, specifically at the Provider level.

8.3. Integration Option 3: Make use of Accounting data :

This is the use case where one wants to make use of the Accounting data collected (e.g Marketplace or Service Registry Dashboards)

Integration Steps:

1. Open a Ticket on EOSC Helpdesk to request to gain access to accounting information by sending:
 - a. The name of the service that requires the information ;
 - b. An email to create the user able to access to the monitoring information;
2. The accounting team will process the request according to the policies and make the necessary configuration so that the user gains read-only access to the required data and provide information and guidance on how to retrieve the information.